

THE IMPACT OF AGROTECHNICAL MEASURES ON PRODUCTIVITY INDICATORS OF TYPICAL IRRIGATED GRAY-SOIL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11262165>

Annotation. The article presents the importance of studying the impact of agrotechnical measures on the productivity of typical irrigated gray-earth soils, changes in the properties of typical irrigated gray-earth soils under the influence of fertilizers. In addition to a sufficient amount of organic and mineral fertilizers in the soil, attention should be paid to improving the soil structure. In order for the soil to be fertile, it is necessary to study its properties, composition and various processes occurring in the soil. The aim is to study the distribution of fertility indicators of typical gray-earth soils, the influence of erosion processes on them, the influence of anthropogenic factors and agrotechnical measures-irrigation, mineral fertilizers, organic fertilizers on soil fertility. Various types of crops, mineral and organic fertilizers affect soil fertility. As a result of the conversion of organic residues, the soil is enriched with nitrogen.

Key words: typical serozem soils, mineral and organic fertilizers, soil fertility.

Currently, there is a need in the Republic of Kyrgyzstan to improve the quality of life, effective and rational work, as well as to improve the quality of life and improve the quality of life. Agrotechnical activities that are important, typical activities that affect specific agrotechnical activities are important for the development of agricultural technology. The cannon of unicumdorligin and Oshirishda uzda vremenikka ishlov Bermasdan Turib, Samarali and Yahshi itojalarga Erishib bulmaidi. What is unique is that the cannon provides a faster development of legitimacy than the cannon. You must take responsibility for creating a unique and unique project for the production of mineral and organic raw materials, special equipment, mining equipment, mining equipment and equipment for the production of organic materials. The organic and mineral cannon can be used throughout the entire range of structural and mechanical bullets. Unique and a unique project for the production of mineral and organic raw materials, special equipment, mining equipment, mining equipment and equipment for the production of organic materials. The organic and mineral cannon can be used throughout the entire range of structural and mechanical bullets. A unique cannon is necessary to teach a specific profession, and a turley cannon is necessary to teach a profession.

Typical saline soils have been occupied by the fall left on different Darajad plains of saballi, this soil has been eroded in different darajas. Soil erosion of the Onda unique-the treasury is being washed away in different darages. Erosion affects the density of humus and

lake material in the amount of keskin kamaib ketadi. Erosion of the heat is a refractory physicist, mechanic, chemist, agrochemist hassalariga salbiy Afzar etadi. As a result, the tuprok of the unidorliga pasaib ketadi. In order to prevent rock erosion and soil erosion, it is necessary to take measures to eliminate soil erosion. The reason for this was gum erosion. A unique approach to studying the composition of humus and lake alkali, the required amount of gel and compound. An agrotechnician engaged in the development of mineral raw materials complexes is an organic and agricultural technician for the production of mineral raw materials complexes. Organic matter strongly influences climate: biological, microbiological and biochemical climate influences the climate of organic material. The unique cannon training course is essential for the education and development of cannon sports in Turkey. The need of agriculture for unique and modern agrotechnological equipment is due to the high level of agricultural development. Gun mechanic ishlov Berishda uning biogenligining development, organic material quantitative kamayeshi, organic composite buzilishi and emirilishiga olib keladi. The result is a unique and less productive cannon. A typical cannon of a unique design and a unique cannon of a unique design are also important. Agrotechnics

A typical ice course of the unique Igor Pushkar is lethal shot blasting, ularga erosion, heat engineering, anthropogenic and agrotechnical measures: sugorish, mineral and organic carbon fiber unicumdorlik kursatkichlaring effective effect of kursatadi. A unique tour of Turkmenistan, a mineral and organic complex. As a result of the organics, a nitrogen cannon was obtained.

The influence of agrochemical and agrophysical properties of irrigated typical rich soils, mechanical composition and application rates of various fertilizers on biochemical processes is presented. It has been studied in many ways that this depends on the vegetation cover on the soil surface, the amount of humus, the mechanical composition of the soil, the pH value of the soil environment and soil biogenicity. Analyzing a number of different processes occurring on typical rich soils irrigated in spring and autumn, it can be concluded that the seasonal dynamics of soil fertility is determined by environmental factors, humidity and temperature. During the spring and autumn periods, hydrothermal conditions were high [1]. The importance of changing soil fertility indicators under the influence of agrotechnical measures lies in the fact that irrigated typical peat soils of the Khududau experimental site, weakly and moderately eroded, have been studied, the mechanical composition consists of medium-sandy soils, weakly eroded. It has been observed that the productivity coefficient on non-eroded soils is higher compared to eroded soils. On irrigated typical rich soils, the fertility level is high in soil layers up to 0-50 cm, low in layers 50-70 cm and very low in layers 70-100 cm and below. In the lower layers of the soil, cut from 0 to 50 cm, soil fertility indicators decrease sharply. This is especially noticeable on eroded soils. Productivity indicators on irrigated typical rich soils differ from each other depending on the time of year - spring and autumn. In the spring season, they are observed higher than in autumn. Soil fertility indicators depend on the content of humus in it, the thickness of the humus layer, the amount of nutrients, the PH of the soil environment, physical, mechanical and agrochemical properties of the soil. The higher the indicators of soil fertility in terms of redox reactions occurring in the soil, air exchange in the soil, nitrogen and phosphorus entering the soil, the biological activity increases soil fertility [1]. It has been shown that if the deadlines, methods and norms of application are correctly observed of mineral and organic fertilizers for growing winter wheat on irrigated loamy soils, then the growth of winter wheat, as well as grain yield and ham

quality will be good [2]. Field experiments, during which conditions are being created to improve the technology of growing winter wheat, provide for the timing and norms of the application of agrotechnical measures for the vegetative development of winter wheat [3]. The purpose of the study: it is supposed to study the change in productivity indicators of irrigated typical rich soils under the influence of agrotechnical measures. The object of the study. Tdau (Expansion Center) of the experimental farm of the Kibraysky district of the Tashkent region for to study the properties of irrigated typical peat soils and changes in productivity indicators under the influence of agrotechnical measures. Morphological features of irrigated typical peat soils TDAU (Expansion Center), along with the study of the mechanical composition, physical, and agrochemical properties of irrigated typical peat soils, also study changes in productivity indicators under the influence of agrotechnical measures [1].

Expected results. It is supposed to study the change in productivity indicators of irrigated typical rich soils under the influence of agrotechnical measures, to study the effect of mineral and organic fertilizers on the growth development of winter wheat, as well as the timing and norms of fertilizer application.

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